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Research Article

**DESIGN AND EVALUATION OF CLOFAZIMINE
NANOCRYSTALS TO IMPROVE ITS ORAL
BIOAVAILABILITY****P. Venkatesh, D. Varun, S. K. Godasu, K. Janaki, P. Deepika**

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Abstract:

The aim of our project has been to develop formulation of Nanocrystals of an anti-leprotic drug Clofazimine, in order to improve its oral bioavailability. Clofazimine nanocrystals were prepared by anti-solvent precipitation method. In vitro data obtained for Clofazimine nanocrystals showed good entrapment efficiency and sustained drug release. From the results it can be concluded that the drug release from the nanocrystals were controlled by the surfactant tween 80. The solubility and in vitro dissolution studies suggested that the nanocrystal formulations can improve the bioavailability of the Clofazimine by improving its solubility and dissolution rate. The in-vitro diffusion studies were performed in phosphate buffer. tween 80 releases 90% of the drug within 3 hrs but in case of PVP and combination of PVP and tween 80, the release was extended to 4 hrs. PVP releases only 80% of drug in 4 hrs but combination of PVP and Tween formulations release maximum amount of drug i.e., 99% within 4 hrs. Hence, it was concluded that nano crystallization was a good approach to enhance the solubility and dissolution property of Clofazimine by nanoprecipitation technique and also sustained the drug release by using Tween 80 as surfactant and PVP as a stabilizer. Thus, nanocrystal drug delivery system can have adopted to increase the solubility and dissolution rate of poorly soluble drug like paclitaxel to enhance their bioavailability.

Key words: Formulation, Optimization, Clofazimine, Nanocrystals, Bioavailability**Corresponding author:****P. Venkatesh,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Over the years, nanoparticles (NPs) made of both organic and inorganic materials have been engineered to circumvent the biological barriers and deliver drugs for a variety of indications.^{1, 2} Water-insoluble or hydrophobic drugs, pose a challenge in terms of achieving optimal bioavailability and thereby, adequate efficacy.³ As reported in 2015, 40% of drugs on the market and 90% of drugs within the discovery pipeline face solubility issues.⁴ Other statistics, cite 40% of all potential drug candidates were shelved as a result of intrinsic aqueous solubility issues.⁵ Thus, a number of hydrophobic drugs, which could potentially be useful for treatments are in need of clinically acceptable carriers.⁶

For the purpose of this review article, drug nanocrystals may be defined as pure solid particles with a mean diameter <1 μm and a crystalline character. The platform offers an exceptional opportunity to deliver hydrophobic drugs. Its uniqueness originates from the fact that nanocrystals are composed entirely of 100% drug or the payload thereby eliminating the ancillary role of a carrier.⁷ In addition, surfactants or stabilizers are commonly used to stabilize the crystalline dispersions in liquid media.

Nanocrystalline drug technology improves the solubility of hydrophobic drugs due to an increased surface area to volume ratio and improved dissolution rates (i.e., dissolution velocity) associated with nanosizing.⁸ The drug crystals are singularly well-suited for the rehabilitation of previously unsuccessful Biopharmaceutics Classification System (BCS) Class II and IV drugs (low solubility drugs).⁹ The BCS classification system is an experimental model that measures permeability and solubility under prescribed conditions. The system divides the drugs into four classes. While Class I drugs have high solubility and high permeability, Class II molecules have low solubility and high permeability, Class III identifies with high solubility and low permeability, and drugs in Class IV have low solubility and low permeability.⁴

Nanocrystal drug formulations have also been shown to be stable in suspensions and are often referred to as nanocrystal colloidal dispersions (NCD's). The dispersions provide a platform for easy scale-up and manufacturing of highly stable and marketable products. Their synthesis and scale-up considerations have been described at length elsewhere.^{10, 11} Commonly used synthesis techniques include the use of microfluidic based platforms or the milling method, which, among others, is both flexible and tunable.^{7, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17} Taken together, the

nanocrystal drug technology has been studied extensively and is well positioned for further exploration in the field of drug delivery.

Several hydrophobic drugs have been salvaged via the nanocrystal formulation method. The drugs were successfully developed, and approved by the FDA to treat a variety of indications ranging from dental disorders to cancer in the clinic.^{14, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28} Depending on the disease, the approved formulations can be administered via different routes including oral, dermal, and parenteral. This highlights the versatility of a nanocrystal drug platform. Pharmacokinetic, biodistribution, and bioavailability data for organs involved in delivery routes tested using nanocrystal technology have been addressed at length previously.^{10, 13, 18, 24, 25, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34} Specifically, the reviews of Lu et al. 2016 and 2017 delve into the biodistribution pattern of nanocrystal drugs in the blood, heart, liver, spleen, lung, kidney, tumor, and thymus (i.e., the organs involved in clearance/circulation and host immune responses).^{24, 35}

Clofazimine is a highly lipophilic antimicrobial riminophenazine dye used in combination with other agents, such as dapsone, for the treatment of leprosy. It was originally described in 1957 and was the prototypical riminophenazine dye - a bright-red dye that, in its clinical use, results in long-lasting discoloration of the skin and bodily fluids. Although it carries *in vitro* activity against other mycobacterium, such as *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, it is generally considered an ineffective treatment in comparison to classic tuberculosis treatments such as rifampicin and isoniazid.³⁶

The aim of our project has been to develop formulation of Nanocrystals of an anti-leprotic drug Clofazimine, in order to improve its oral bioavailability.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY:

MATERIALS

Clofazimine, Tween 80, PVP, Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) Procured from Sigma Aldrich.

METHODOLOGY

Solubility Study by Equilibrium Solubility Method

Solubility studies of Clofazimine were performed by equilibrating excess amount of drug in water, ethanol, acetone and methanol. Assays were carried out in screw capped vials and samples were kept in orbital shaker (Remi, India) at 37 °C for 24 hours (to achieve the equilibrium condition). After this interval, samples

were filtered through 0.45 μm membrane filter and diluted in volumetric flask with solvent followed by quantification using UV-Vi's spectrophotometer at 256nm.

Determination of Absorption Maxima (λ_{max}) and standard graph

Clofazimine 10mg was transferred to 100ml volumetric flask, dissolved in little amount of DMSO and final volume is made up with DMSO (stock solution). All the concentrations are prepared by taking 10 ml from above solution was taken into another 100ml volumetric flask and volume was made up with DMSO (2° stock solution). Volumes of 2ml, 5ml, 10ml, 15ml & 20ml were taken in 10ml volumetric flask from the 2°stock solution and diluted up to the mark with DMSO. The absorbance of the above solutions is analyzed using Shimadzu UV-visible spectrometer and the λ_{max} was found. The calibration curve is prepared by plotting concentration versus absorbance as shown in the Figure.

FT-IR Spectroscopy:

FTIR spectroscopy is usually considered as imperative analytical technique for identification of API, since FTIR spectra exhibits characteristic peaks, indicating presence of various functional groups in the product. FTIR spectra of Clofazimine were obtained by KBr pellet method on a FTIR spectrometer (Jasco 6100, Tokyo, Japan) with resolution of 2 cm^{-1} . The data is presented as the average of 16 scans which were recorded over the range 4000–400 cm^{-1} . The confirmation of the identity of compound was ascertained by comparison of the FTIR spectra of pharmacopeial standard spectra.

Formulation development

Formulation	Drug (mg)	PVP (mg)	Tween 80 (ml)	DMSO (ml)	Water (ml)
F1	100	223	-	22	22
F2	100	446	-	22	22
F3	100	892	-	22	22
F4	100	-	2.47	22	22
F5	100	-	4.94	22	22
F6	100	-	9.88	22	22
F7	100	111.5	1.235	22	22
F8	100	223	2.47	22	22
F9	100	446	4.94	22	22

Table 1: Formulation design

Formulations were prepared using different types of stabilizers, solvent and Anti-solvent. From the results obtained

Selection of Solvent

Based on the solubility studies of Clofazimine in different solvents it was observed that dimethyl sulfoxide [52 mg/ml], ethanol [25mg/ml] and Polyethylene glycol [20mg/mL] have a good solubility. As Clofazimine had good solubility in dimethyl sulfoxide, it was selected as solvent.

Selection of Anti-solvent

Based on the solubility data distilled water was selected as antisolvent as it has very low solubility of 0.6 mg/mL and also miscibility with the selected solvent.

Selection of surfactant

Several stabilizers were tested for stabilizing the nanocrystal preparation by being respectively added to drug solution. Surfactants improve the physical stability of nanocrystals by reduce Ostwald's ripening. Three **different** surfactants were evaluated as stabilizers. Egg Lecithin, Tween 80 and Glycerol Mono oleate were evaluated at different drug: Surfactant molar ratios of 1:1, 1:2, 1:4 and 1:8. Among all the surfactants Tween 80 was selected for further studies.

Selection of polymer:

The polymers were selected on the basis of to evaluate is PVA as its approved by US FDA for usage in Injectable dosage forms and provide the controlled release of drug for longer periods.

Method of preparation

Nanocrystals of Clofazimine were prepared by nano precipitation technique or anti-solvent precipitation technique. All the materials are weighed according to their molar mass (Table). The samples are prepared by varying the ratios of surfactant and stabilizer. Firstly, Clofazimine is dissolved in DMSO which is then placed on a magnetic stirrer. Now weighed amount of stabilizer, surfactant and stabilizer-surfactant are added to the above solutions accordingly to the ratios calculated. Once all the materials are dissolved add the anti-solvent drop wise, after 45mins of stirring it appears a cloudy suspension. Now filter the solution, collect the residue and filtrate for further studies.

Drug pay load

A drug pay load study gives the information about the actual amount of drug present in the formulation. Take 20mg of Clofazimine nanocrystals of each formulation in a 10ml volumetric flask and make up the volume with methanol (2000 μ g/ml). Take 1ml of above solution in 10ml volumetric flask and make up the volume with methanol (200 μ g/ml). Similarly take 1ml from above solution in another 10ml volumetric flask and make up the volume with methanol (20 μ g/ml). Now check the absorbance of the final solution in UV-Visible Spectrophotometer.³⁹ With the help of absorbance calculate the concentration using standard plot of Clofazimine and calculate the drug pay load values using the following equation.

Particle Size, Polydispersity index and Zeta Potential Determination

The particle size distribution of different nanocrystals was observed using a Mastersizer 2000 (Malvern Instruments Ltd, Worcestershire, UK) to access the size range and uniformity of particle size distribution in the formulation. The samples were suitably diluted with Milli Q water for every measurement. The zeta potential of the same was determined using a Zetasizer (Malvern Instruments Ltd, Worcestershire, UK). The instrument was operated at a constant temperature of 25 °C using a clear disposable zeta cell. The mean diameter and polydispersity index (PI) of the particles were calculated using the cumulant analysis after averaging the three measurements.³⁸

Particle morphology- Inverse phase microscopy

Inverse phase microscopy (Olympus, model - AxioCamERc 5s, Japan) was initially used to

characterize the particle size of the drug nanocrystals. One drop of diluted paclitaxel nanocrystal suspension was deposited on a clean slide and placed a cover slip gently over the drop at an angle, with one edge touching the slide and removed the excess liquid and air bubbles. Then the slide is placed onto the stage of the microscope. Observed the shape of crystals under microscope using 40 x eyepieces and captured the images by using Motic Image software.

In-Vitro Diffusion Studies

Diffusion studies of Clofazimine nanocrystals were performed using egg as semi-permeable membrane. Prior to it the semi-permeable membrane is collected from an egg by placing the egg in concentrated HCl till the shell dissolves. Once the shell is dissolved the semi-permeable is washed and is tied to one of the open ends of inner tube. Then a 20mg of each formulation Clofazimine nanocrystals were weighed and are mixed in 10ml of phosphate buffer which are then poured into the inner tube of diffusion apparatus. The outer chamber is filled with 100ml of phosphate buffer and the inner tube is placed carefully into the outer tube. Now the setup is placed on magnetic stirrer (to resemble the physiological peristaltic moments) and samples are collected at regular intervals of time as shown in the Table. All the samples are checked for absorbance in UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The absorbance obtained is used to calculate the percentage drug release and a graph is plotted by taking time on X-axis and Percentage drug release on Y-axis.³⁷

X-ray Diffraction (XRD) Analysis

The characteristics of the Clofazimine nanocrystals and pure Clofazimine were analyzed by powder XRD (D8 Advance; Bruker Optik, Ettlingen, Germany) with Cu source of radiation. Measurements were carried out at a voltage of 40kV and 25mA. The scanned angle was performed from 2.5° to 60°, and the scanning rate was 2°/minute.³⁷

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Solubility:

The solubility of pure drug in different solvents was carried out by dissolving the drug at saturated levels and it reveals that the drug is completely insoluble in water and propylene glycol, slightly soluble in poly ethylene glycol, soluble in dichloromethane, ethanol, n-methyl pyrrolidone and isopropyl alcohol.

Figure 1: Solubility of Clofazimine in different solvents

Lambda (λ) max of Clofazimine

Lambda max refers to the wavelength in the absorption spectrum where the absorbance is **maximum**. Generally, molecules absorb in a wavelength range centered around the **lambda max**. It acts as a single quantitative parameter to compare the absorption range of different molecules. The Lambda maximum obtained is **256nm** and it was shown in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2: λ max of Clofazimine

Standard graph of Clofazimine

The obtained results for the standard graph of antileprosy drug Clofazimine was shown in **Figure 3**.

Figure 3: Standard plot of Clofazimine

Table 2: Standard table of Clofazimine

Sl. No	Sample	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Wavelength (nm)
1	G1	2.000	0.090
2	G2	5.000	0.238
3	G3	10.000	0.501
4	G4	15.000	0.719
5	G5	20.000	0.927

Drug-Excipients Interaction studies by FTIR

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy was carried out to identify the possible interactions between the drug and hydrophilic carriers in prepared solid systems. Samples of CFZ, carriers, and their preparations were characterized by FTIR spectroscopy (Shimadzu 8400, Japan) using the potassium bromide (KBr) pellet method (Prokopowicz et al., 2014). The scanning range was 4000-400 cm^{-1} at a resolution of 1 cm^{-1} .

FT-IR spectra of Clofazimine

The FTIR spectra of Clofazimine are as in figure 4.

Figure 4: FT IR spectrum of Clofazimine

In FTIR technique, IR radiation is passed through a sample. A part of the IR radiation is absorbed by the sample and the remaining is transmitted. The resulting spectrum characterizes the molecular absorption and transmission,

producing a molecular fingerprint of the sample. Like a fingerprint no two unique molecular structures produce the same IR spectrum. This makes infrared spectroscopy useful for several types of analysis. Figure 2 depicted the spectrum of pure CFZ characteristic peaks at 1563.9, 1516.5, 1302.2, 1090.3, 820 and 745.9 cm^{-1} .

Table 3: Characteristics peaks of Clofazimine:

Frequency (cm^{-1})	Interpretation
1563.9,1516.5, 1302.2	Aromatic CH stretching
1090.3,820, 745.9	CH(CH ₃) ₂ stretching

The characteristic peaks of the drug sample matched with the reported values of characteristic peaks of CFZ. Therefore, the sample was assumed to be pure in nature and suitable for further use. **Particle Size, Polydispersity index and Zeta Potential Determination**

The particle size analysis of 9 different nanocrystal formulations revealed that the average particle size measured by laser light scattering method is around 80-100 nm with low polydispersity index. The particle size distribution of these formulations is unimodal and has a narrow range as shown in the Table 6 indicates that the formulations would be stable and the tendency to agglomerate would be miniscule. A narrow PI means that the colloidal suspensions are homogenous in nature.

Table 4: Particle Size, Polydispersity index and Zeta Potential

Sample	Mean diameter \pm SD (nm)	Polydispersity Index	Zeta potential (mV)
F1	82.18 \pm 2.26	0.212 \pm 0.005	-22.3 \pm 4.89
F2	90.14 \pm 1.45	0.237 \pm 0.005	-21.7 \pm 5.48
F3	92.26 \pm 10.2	0.220 \pm 0.005	-26.2 \pm 5.14
F4	93.17 \pm 7.25	0.263 \pm 0.005	-23.3 \pm 6.75
F5	84.58 \pm 2.26	0.222 \pm 0.005	-29.3 \pm 3.19
F6	91.24 \pm 3.25	0.247 \pm 0.005	-27.7 \pm 2.24
F7	94.44 \pm 8.02	0.240 \pm 0.005	-28.2 \pm 1.23
F8	92.57 \pm 6.75	0.293 \pm 0.005	-24.3 \pm 7.12
F9	86.21 \pm .26	0.282 \pm 0.005	-28.8 \pm 8.22

Particle morphology

Micrograph from the inverse phase microscopy shows that clofazimine nanocrystals were in the range of 100–150 nm. The dried Clofazimine nanocrystals appeared as an orange powder. As shown in Figure 13, many irregular particles were observed. Formulations with combination of Tween 80 and PVP resulted in nanoparticles with regular crystalline structure with a particular order.

Figure 5: Microscopic images of prepared nanocrystals

Drug pay load

The drug payload values are shown in the table below. The values described that tween80 has shown the highest drug pay load values when compared to PVP and combination. Among which 1:4:4 ratio of Drug: PVP: tween80 has shown the maximum drug pay load values. The drug pay load values of all the formulations are given below in **Table.5**.

Table 5: Drug pay load values

F1	D:PVP	1:2	82%
F2	D:PVP	1:4	83.1%
F3	D:PVP	1:8	80.1%
F4	D:T-80	1:2	85.5%
F5	D:T-80	1:4	86%
F5	D:T-80	1:8:	84.2%
F7	D:P:T	1:1:1	87.5%
F8	D:P:T	1:2:2	88.2%
F9	D:P:T	1:4:4	89%

In-vitro diffusion studies

As shown in the table below the diffusion studies of all the formulations are performed and results are reported. The *in-vitro* diffusion studies were performed in phosphate buffer. Tween 80 releases 90% of the drug within 3 hrs but in case of PVP and combination of PVP whereas tween 80 the release was extended to 4 hrs. PVP releases only 80% of drug in 4 hrs but combination of PVP and Tween 80 formulations release maximum amount of drug i.e., 99% within

4 hrs. It is also shown that among the 3 ratios 1:4 has shown the best drug release than 1:2 and 1:8. The values are shown in **Table 6** and A graph is plotted between time versus percentage drug release as shown in **Figure 7**. The results elucidated that in the combination the release of drug is enhanced and also extended when compared to the PVP and Tween 80.

Table 6: In-vitro Diffusion Studies

Time (min)	Drug:PVP			Drug: Tween80			Drug: PVP : Tween80		
	1:2	1:4	1:8	1:2	1:4	1:8	1:1:1	1:2:2	1:4:4
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	0.64 ±1.52	1.92 ±0.36	1.68 ±0.14	4.4 ±1.43	6.8 ±1.35	5.1 ±0.22	3.6 ±0.42	5.8 ±0.28	6.2 ±1.27
10	6.8 ±0.62	10.5 ±0.25	9.9 ±0.43	10.3 ±2.21	15.2 ±0.10	19.4 ±1.23	8.2 ±0.30	9.4 ±1.87	10.9 ±0.69
15	13.4 ±0.20	14.3 ±0.21	13.9 ±2.62	20.6 ±0.64	24.3 ±0.71	22.2 ±0.51	13.3 ±0.71	15.1 ±0.27	16.6 ±1.93
30	20.3 ±1.20	20.1 ±6.15	20.2 ±0.49	30.2 ±0.82	36.4 ±0.46	34.3 ±0.24	16.4 ±0.69	19.8 ±0.81	21.1 ±0.92
45	25.1 ±2.30	27.5 ±1.04	28.1 ±1.23	39.9 ±0.23	45.3 ±2.48	41.2 ±1.61	20.1 ±1.47	22.3 ±1.17	27.3 ±1.23
60	34.3 ±0.68	35.7 ±1.02	34.8 ±0.55	48.3 ±0.46	54.8 ±0.78	50.4 ±0.59	31.3 ±0.74	35.4 ±0.63	39.7 ±0.59
90	42.2 ±0.96	43.1 ±3.38	42.6 ±0.62	59.9 ±1.23	65.2 ±0.85	61.2 ±0.29	39.8 ±0.26	42.1 ±0.63	44.1 ±0.37
120	52.6 ±1.23	55.6 ±0.35	53.2 ±1.23	79.1 ±1.53	78.9 ±3.37	81.4 ±0.64	61.4 ±0.62	64.3 ±1.23	69.4 ±0.44
180	63.4 ±2.56	70.1 ±0.41	69.4 ±1.72	92.1 ±1.62	98.2 ±1.80	95.9 ±3.27	80.2 ±0.42	83.1 ±0.93	85.3 0.37
240	75.4 ±0.92	80.8 ±2.55	80.1 ±0.84				97.2 ±1.23	98.4 ±1.32	99.2 ±0.68

Figure 6: In-vitro Diffusion Studies

X-Ray powder Diffraction

XRD is a non-destructive technique to measure the average spacing between the layers or rows of atoms. It identifies the orientation of a single crystal. It is helpful in finding the crystal structure of an unknown material. With the help of XRD, we can measure the size, shape and internal stress of small crystalline regions. CFZ is crystalline in nature and it exists in both monoclinic and triclinic crystal forms.

Characteristic XRD peaks are obtained with CFZ. Thus, XRD could be used to study any changes in crystallinity of the drug. The powder X-ray diffraction pattern of the procured drug (Figure 3), indicated the crystalline nature of CFZ. Sharp and intense crystalline peaks with relative intensity of 64.41% and 100% were observed to be at 2 thetas of 9.22° and 21.85° in the diffraction spectrum of CFZ

Figure 7: XRD pattern of pure drug – clofazimine

Figure 8: XRD pattern of Clofazimine nanocrystals

SUMMARY

Clofazimine nanocrystals were prepared by anti-solvent precipitation method. In vitro data obtained for Clofazimine nanocrystals showed good entrapment efficiency and sustained drug release. From the results it can be concluded that the drug release from the nanocrystals were controlled by the surfactant tween 80. The solubility and in vitro dissolution studies suggested that the nanocrystal formulations can improve the bioavailability of the Clofazimine by improving its solubility and dissolution rate. The in-vitro diffusion studies were performed in phosphate buffer. tween 80 releases 90% of the drug within 3 hrs but in case of PVP and combination of PVP and tween 80, the release was extended to 4 hrs. PVP releases only 80% of drug in 4 hrs but combination of PVP and Tween formulations release maximum amount of drug i.e., 99% within 4 hrs.

CONCLUSION:

Hence, it was concluded that nano crystallization was a good approach to enhance the solubility and dissolution property of Clofazimine by nanoprecipitation technique and also sustained the drug release by using Tween 80 as surfactant and PVP as a stabilizer. Thus, nanocrystal drug delivery system can have adopted to increase the solubility and dissolution rate of poorly soluble drug like paclitaxel to enhance their bioavailability.

REFERENCES:

1. De Jong WH, Borm PJA. Drug delivery and nanoparticles: applications and hazards. *Int J Nanomedicine*. 2008;3:133-149. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
2. Bae YH, Park K. Targeted drug delivery to tumors: myths, reality and possibility. *J Control Release*. 2011;153:198-205. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
3. Muller RH, Keck CM. Challenges and solutions for the delivery of biotech drugs – a review of drug nanocrystal technology and lipid nanoparticles. *J Biotechnol*. 2004;113:151-170. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
4. Sonvico F, Mornet S, Vasseur S, et al. Folate-conjugated iron oxide nanoparticles for solid tumor targeting as potential specific magnetic hyperthermia mediators: synthesis, physicochemical characterization, and in vitro experiments. *Bioconj Chem*. 2005;16:1181-1188. 10.1021/BC050050Z. [[PubMed](#)] [[CrossRef](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
5. Savjani KT, Gajjar AK, Savjani JK. Drug solubility: importance and enhancement techniques. *ISRN Pharm*. 2012;2012:195727. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
6. Anselmo AC, Mitragotri S. An overview of clinical and commercial impact of drug delivery systems. *J Control Release*. 2014;190:15-28. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
7. Junghanns J, Müller R. Nanocrystal technology, drug delivery and clinical applications. *Int J Nanomed*. 2008;3(3):295-309. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
8. Tuomela A, Saarinen J, Strachan CJ, Hirvonen J. Production, applications and in vivo fate of drug nanocrystals. *J Drug Deliv Sci Technol*. 2016;34:21-31. [[Google Scholar](#)]

9. US Department of Health and Human Services, Food and Drug Administration Center for Drug Evaluation and Research . Waiver of in vivo bioavailability and bioequivalence studies for immediate-release solid Oral dosage forms based on a biopharmaceutics classification system guidance for industry. *Biopharmaceutics*. 2017;1-19. [[Google Scholar](#)]
10. Pawar VK, Singh Y, Meher JG, Gupta S, Chourasia MK. Engineered nanocrystal technology: in-vivo fate, targeting and applications in drug delivery. *J Control Release*. 2014;183:51-66. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
11. George J, Sabapathi SN. Cellulose nanocrystals: synthesis, functional properties, and applications. *Nanotechnol Sci Appl*. 2015;8:45-54. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
12. Wang X, Zhuang J, Peng Q, Li Y. A general strategy for nanocrystal synthesis. *Nature*. 2005;437:121-124. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
13. Malamataris M, Taylor KMG, Malamataris S, Douroumis D, Kachrimanis K. Pharmaceutical nanocrystals: production by wet milling and applications. *Drug Discov Today*. 2018;23:534-547. 10.1016/J.DRUDIS.2018.01.016. [[PubMed](#)] [[CrossRef](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
14. Lu Y, Chen Y, Gemeinhart RA, Wu W, Li T. Developing nanocrystals for cancer treatment. *Nanomedicine*. 2015;10:2537-2552. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
15. Van Eerdenbrugh B, Van den Mooter G, Augustijns P. Top-down production of drug nanocrystals: nanosuspension stabilization, miniaturization and transformation into solid products. *Int J Pharm*. 2008;364:64-75. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
16. Boleininger J, Kurz A, Reuss V, Sönnichsen C. Microfluidic continuous flow synthesis of rod-shaped gold and silver nanocrystals. *Phys Chem Chem Phys*. 2006;8:3824-3827. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
17. Peltonen L, Hirvonen J. Pharmaceutical nanocrystals by nanomilling: critical process parameters, particle fracturing and stabilization methods. *J Pharm Pharmacol*. 2010;62:1569-1579. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
18. Gao L, Liu G, Ma J, et al. Application of drug nanocrystal technologies on oral drug delivery of poorly soluble drugs. *Pharm Res*. 2013;30:307-324. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
19. Gao L, Liu G, Ma J, Wang X, Zhou L, Li X. Drug nanocrystals: in vivo performances. *J Control Release*. 2012;160:418-430. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
20. Chen H, Khemtong C, Yang X, Chang X, Gao J. Nanonization strategies for poorly water-soluble drugs. *Drug Discov Today*. 2011;16:354-360. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
21. Brough C, Williams RO. Amorphous solid dispersions and nano-crystal technologies for poorly water-soluble drug delivery. *Int J Pharm*. 2013;453:157-166. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
22. Kalepu S, Nekkanti V. Insoluble drug delivery strategies: review of recent advances and business prospects. *Acta Pharm Sin B*. 2015;5:442-453. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
23. Lee BK, Yun YH, Park K. Smart nanoparticles for drug delivery: boundaries and opportunities. *Chem Eng Sci*. 2015;125:158-164. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
24. Lu Y, Li Y, Wu W. Injected nanocrystals for targeted drug delivery. *Acta Pharm Sin B*. 2016;6:106-113. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
25. Merisko-Liversidge E, Liversidge GG. Nanosizing for oral and parenteral drug delivery: a perspective on formulating poorly-water soluble compounds using wet media milling technology. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev*. 2011;63:427-440. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
26. Miao X, Yang W, Feng T, Lin J, Huang P. Drug nanocrystals for cancer therapy. *Wiley Interdiscip Rev Nanomed Nanobiotechnol*. 2017;10:e1499. 10.1002/wnan.1499. [[PubMed](#)] [[CrossRef](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
27. Möschwitzer JP. Drug nanocrystals in the commercial pharmaceutical development process. *Int J Pharm*. 2013;453:142-156. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
28. Peltonen L, Hirvonen J. Drug nanocrystals – versatile option for formulation of poorly soluble materials. *Int J Pharm*. 2018;537:73-83. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
29. Shegokar R, Müller RH. Nanocrystals: industrially feasible multifunctional formulation technology for poorly soluble actives. *Int J Pharm*. 2010;399:129-139. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
30. Su H, Wang Y, Gu Y, Bowman L, Zhao J, Ding M. Potential applications and human biosafety of nanomaterials used in nanomedicine. *J Appl Toxicol*. 2018;38:3-24. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
31. Lu PS, Inbaraj BS, Chen BH. Determination of oral bioavailability of curcuminoid dispersions and nanoemulsions prepared from *Curcuma*

- longa* Linnaeus. *J Sci Food Agric*. 2018;98:51-63. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
32. Maudens P, Seemayer CA, Thauvin C, Gabay C, Jordan O, Allémann E. Nanocrystal-polymer particles: extended delivery carriers for osteoarthritis treatment. *Small*. 2018;14:1703108 10.1002/sml.201703108. [[PubMed](#)] [[CrossRef](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
33. He Y, Xia DN, Li QX, Tao JS, Gan Y, Wang C. Enhancement of cellular uptake, transport and oral absorption of protease inhibitor saquinavir by nanocrystal formulation. *Acta Pharmacol Sin*. 2015;36:1151-1160. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
34. Koshani R, Madadlou A. A viewpoint on the gastrointestinal fate of cellulose nanocrystals. *Trends Food Sci Technol*. 2018;71:268-273. [[Google Scholar](#)]
35. Lu Y, Qi J, Dong X, Zhao W, Wu W. The in vivo fate of nanocrystals. *Drug Discov Today*. 2017;22:744-750. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
36. Cholo MC, Steel HC, Fourie PB, Germishuizen WA, Anderson R: Clofazimine: current status and future prospects. *J Antimicrob Chemother*. 2012 Feb;67(2):290-8. doi: 10.1093/jac/dkr444. Epub 2011 Oct 20. (PubMed ID 22020137)
37. Peng-Fei-Yue ,Yu Li ,Jing Wan ,Youg Wang , Ming Yang ,Wei-Fong Zhu, Chang-Hong Vong , Hai Zong Yuah. Process optimization and evaluation of novel baicalin solid nanocrystals. *International Journal of Nanomedicine*.
38. Zahra Bastami, Azade Taheri1, Shahla Soltanpour2. Formulation, optimization and characterization of gemfibrozil nanocrystals prepared by wet milling technique. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutics* - January-March 2015.
39. Huaxi Xiaoa, Tao Yanga, Qinlu Lina, *, Gao-Qiang Liua,*, Lin Zhanga, Fengxiang Yub, Yuejiao Chena. Acetylated starch nanocrystals: Preparation and antitumor drug delivery study. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules* 89 (2016) 456–464.